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**Health Literacy Interventions, Self-Efficacy and
Physiologic Measures Among Adults with Diabetes
in a Tertiary Hospital in Ilocos Norte, Philippines**

**MAITA GRETCHEN A. NAJERA
2000-53458**

**Dr. Araceli O. Balabagno
Adviser**

Abstract

The study explored the association of outcome variables such as self-efficacy and physiologic measures (capillary blood sugar and blood pressure) before and after a health-literacy intervention on diabetes and hypertension. The research focused on health literacy, which is a major contributor and a fundamental factor in the development of public health interventions, and how it relates to managing diabetes. Low health literacy has been linked to lower self-management behaviors and poor medication adherence in diabetic patients.

A pretest-posttest one-group study was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of diabetes health literacy intervention. Subjects were recruited using purposive sampling with the following inclusion criteria: (1) DM type II patients with hypertension stage II as comorbidity aged 18 years old to 60 years old seen at the outpatient department of a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte, (2) diagnosed with diabetes mellitus type II and hypertension stage II for at least one year, (3) able to write and read and can be helped to fill in the questionnaire, (4) willing to participate, and (5) patients who have and who were willing to purchase their own BP apparatus and glucometer or have access to centers where BP and CBG monitoring were done as instructed. Moreover, the study was conducted in a 200-bed capacity tertiary level teaching and training hospital in Ilocos Norte that provides clinical care and management on the prevailing diseases in the area, as well as specialized and sub-specialized forms of treatment, surgical procedure, and intensive care. It is the only Medical Center situated in Northern Luzon, which caters to the provinces of Ilocos Norte, Ilocos Sur, Abra, Northern Cagayan as well as Kalinga Apayao. Data were collected for three months, and participants were recruited by means of posters that were put up in front of the clinics.

Significant findings revealed that self-efficacy is low before health literacy intervention, whereas it is higher after the intervention. Likewise, systolic blood pressure is high before intervention, and low after health literacy intervention. Capillary blood sugar is high before the health literacy intervention, whereas it is

lower after the health literacy intervention. Age, sex, and diet are not significantly related to self-efficacy, blood pressure and capillary blood sugar. Moreover, education and duration of diabetes is significant to their self-efficacy, blood pressure, and capillary blood sugar. Meanwhile, the implementation of a health literacy intervention is hindered by lack of support for the study, shortage of respondents, and the withdrawal of respondents. In addition, successful recruitment of participants via rapport, passionate health care workers, willingness to persuade patients to engage, and optimal scheduling were all variables that helped administer the health literacy treatments. Health literacy intervention in self-efficacy improves self-care management among type 2 adult diabetic patients. The intervention provided interactions with nurses providing education support to engage towards self-care behaviors.

This study recommends that health literacy intervention may be implemented to support the goals of diabetes education to manage their symptoms and that similar health literacy intervention may be considered to other diseases preferably among the top ten causes of mortality and morbidity.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Health Intervention, Experimental Design, Self-Efficacy, Health Literacy Intervention

CHAPTER I: THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Health Literacy Interventions, Self-Efficacy and Physiologic Measures Among Adults with Diabetes in a Tertiary Hospital in Ilocos Norte, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disorder with associated significant morbidity and mortality leading to increasing health care cost. Control of blood sugar and prevention of complications are the cornerstone of therapy. This study will identify issues that contribute to glycemic control and control of blood pressure, and the effects of health literacy intervention to self-efficacy and outcome measures of patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes with stage 2 hypertension as comorbidity.

Diabetes is characterized by high blood sugar or hyperglycemia. It occurs when the body does not produce enough insulin (hormone produced by the pancreas) or when the body's cells do not efficiently react to insulin. This means that the cells do not accept as much glucose from the blood as they supposed to. The cells resist the effects of insulin. Consequently, glucose starts to build up in the blood and is no longer used as fuel for energy. This condition causes hardening and narrowing of arteries putting blood flow at risk and making blood pressure elevate. According to Ohishi (2018), diabetes and hypertension are closely related diseases. Diabetes increases the total amount of fluid in the body and can also decrease the ability of the blood vessel to stretch subsequently causing high blood pressure. A study of Long and Jack (2013) cited that 75% of adults with diabetes also have hypertension and hypertensive patients alone, have showed evidence of insulin resistance. Hence, diabetes and hypertension are two common diseases that co-exist because they have overlapping risk factors such as genetics, following an unhealthy diet, and living an inactive lifestyle. These intertwined conditions can markedly increase the risk of having cardiovascular disease (CVD). Based on the data of the American Diabetes Association, CVD is at least two times more frequent in hypertensive patients with diabetes than in those who are hypertensive alone. According to the World health statistics 2012 report of the World Health Organization, one in three adults

worldwide has hypertension while one in ten adults has diabetes. The global prevalence of diabetes has dramatically increased in a three-decade period from 108 million in 1980 to 422 million in 2014 while the number of people with uncontrolled hypertension from 1980 to 2008 increased from 600 million to almost 1 billion. In the Philippines, the Food and Nutrition Research Institute of the Department of Science and Technology (FNRI-DOST) conducted its 8th National Nutrition Survey from June 2013-April 2014. Based on the Clinical Health Component of the survey, the hypertension rate among Filipino adults slightly decreased from 25.3% (from 7th National Nutrition Survey of the FNRI in 2008) to 22.3% while that of diabetes significantly increased from 4.8% prevalence in 2008 to 5.3% in 2013. Hypertension and the increase in diabetes prevalence rate bring cardiovascular complications to Filipino adults.

At present, there are increasing number of patients with diabetes and hypertension being admitted in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte. Based on the data gathered from the Records Section of the institution, in 2015 there were 38 admitted patients with diabetes and hypertension, 64 cases in 2016, and 87 in the year 2017. As with the Outpatient consultations, there is also an increasing trend, 218 cases were reported in 2015, 248 patients in 2016, while there were 286 a year after.

With the increasing prevalence of diabetic patients with hypertension and being considered as emerging health problems, the goal is to achieve glycemic and blood pressure control through self-care activities, such as adherence to medications, blood glucose and blood pressure monitoring, and having a healthy lifestyle through a good balance between exercise and nutritious diet. These self-care activities are essential to diabetic patients with high blood pressure to maintain and improve their health and prevent disabling and even life-threatening complications. Adherence to these practices is important to prevent or reduce hospitalizations and visits to the emergency department and this would mean better overall health, quality of life, improved clinical outcomes, and reduced healthcare cost. Thus, there are many implications for nurses to promote patients' adherence to the recommended self-care activities.

Nirla Guedes, et. al. (2012) mentioned in their study that nurses have an essential role in the detection, monitoring, treatment and prevention of diseases and in health promotion in the community and among the interventions that are used to promote health in diabetic patients were health education and patient empowerment. Nurses play an essential role in ensuring that patients understand various health issues that are related to their well being through health education that would increase patients' knowledge and improve their personal perception about their health thus improving their health-literacy. According to the study of Kassahun, et.al. (2016), the provision of health education involving self-care and good adherence to medications has been acknowledged to be a cost-effective strategy for improving quality of life of diabetes patients. Patients having good knowledge and education can reduce diabetes and complications by enhancing their self-care behaviors and enabling them to adhere to their regimen effectively.

This study aims to improve patient-centered education emphasizing self-management and empowerment for patients with diabetes and hypertension and consequently to improve the relationship between the patients and the healthcare providers. Its goal is also to explore the outcome variables such as self-efficacy and physiologic measures (capillary blood sugar and blood pressure) before and after a health-literacy intervention on diabetes and hypertension.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Burdened by the self-care practices, a patient with chronic disease often finds it difficult to adhere to the recommended management. It was mentioned in the study of Mayer in 2007 that the factors affecting their non-adherence are, their perception of the disease, lack of understanding of the benefits of treatments, lack of confidence in performing the self-care activities, psychological factors as well as quality of social support that they experience. The study of Shrivastava et. al. (2013) revealed very poor adherence to diabetes treatment regimens is due to poor attitude towards the disease and poor health literacy among the general public.

Based on the anecdotes of diabetic patients in the Emergency Room of the research setting, they have uncontrolled blood sugar because they lack understanding and knowledge about their disease and the importance of compliance to their treatment plan. Some patients have a feeling of inadequacy in terms of managing their diabetes on their own that is why this is a great time to intervene.

Diabetes is a chronic disease, which can be self-managed however this can only be achieved based on the knowledge and elimination of barriers that patients encounter. There are strategies that can help patients remove these burdens and one of these is the health literacy intervention. An intervention that helps patients obtain, process, understand health information and services necessary to make the right health decisions.

A patient's understanding of disease severity and benefit of self-care activities has a significant effect on self-efficacy. It was mentioned in the study of Kassahun, et.al. (2016) that having a good knowledge and education influences good care and can significantly reduce disease complications because it empowers the patients to adhere to their treatment efficiently.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To determine the self-efficacy before and after the health literacy intervention on adults with diabetes in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte.
2. To determine the physiologic outcome measures in terms of glycemic and blood pressure control before and after the health literacy intervention on adults with diabetes in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte.
3. To determine the relationship between self-efficacy and profile characteristics (age, sex, education, diet, and duration of diabetes) of adults with diabetes in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte.
4. To determine the relationship between relationship between physiologic outcome measures and profile characteristics (age, sex, education, diet, and duration of diabetes) of adults with diabetes in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study will help nurses identify issues that contribute to poor glycemic control among diabetic patients. In determining these issues and understanding why diabetic patients are unable to achieve adequate glycemic control, we can find solutions to fill gaps in diabetes self-management.

In the health literacy intervention, nurses' main task is to educate patients so that they will have the knowledge about the nature of the disease and that they will be equipped with information why self-care practices are important. Actively involving diabetic patients in their own care is the foundation of good diabetes management reason why there is a need to update them with best practices about diabetes care through this intervention.

With this study, nurses will act as advocates of the health of diabetic patients and will be more empowered to serve patients who are not receiving education. They will exert more effort to deliver quality care and education then find satisfaction in assisting and developing programs in improving self-efficacy of patients as well as physiologic measures that will help in reducing or preventing complications thereby reducing utilization of health care resources.

SCOPE AND LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study sought to improve the outcomes on self-efficacy and physiologic measures among adult hypertensive diabetic outpatients through health literacy intervention only in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte and this was limited to one cohort group from the province.

CHAPTER II: THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The purpose of the literature review is to gain understanding of information available related to the problem. Initial searches were started in 2011 and repeated for new references in 2018 using ScienceDirect, PubMed, and Google Scholar databases Search items included were, health literacy, self-efficacy, and physiologic measures. The literature review was organized according to the

variables of this study.

Interventions have been done to significantly reduce patients' blood sugar and blood pressure. One of which is the promotion of physical activity in a community in India as studied by Lakshminarayanan, et. al. in 2012. Participants were asked to engage in exercise of moderate intensity in the form of brisk walking for 10 weeks. Although, it had a positive result of reducing the blood sugar and blood pressure, the drop out rate in this study was high. Another intervention identified in improving glycemic control of diabetes patients is the integration of nutrition to physical activity by Asaad, et. al. (2016) conducted in Canada and this study showed favorable result of improving the glycemic control and diet quality of diabetic patients. Mainly, this study focused on nutrition education and healthy eating patterns.

With this study, the function of nurses as health educators was highlighted. Nurses play many roles in the healthcare, however one of the most important responsibilities of a nurse is that of being a patient educator. Patients interact with nurses constantly as compared to the other members of the healthcare team reason why nurses are considered as the best source of patient education. The main concern is to deliver educational intervention with the goal of preventing complications caused by elevated blood sugar and blood pressure levels. Along with the other types of interventions, improving the health literacy of patients through education can potentially change patients' health beliefs, which can lead to change in behavior such as being compliant and adherent to self-management activities.

Health Literacy

Health literacy is significant in health promotion especially in the prevention and treatment of chronic diseases such as diabetes and hypertension. To manage these conditions, patients must be able to access, comprehend, evaluate, and apply health information on a daily basis for improved health. In a study of Orden (2013) about linking health literacy to better asthma control, it was found out that health literacy influences asthma control and quality of life.

Participants with higher health literacy had better asthma-related quality of life and improved disease control than those with lower health literacy.

In a study by Vandebosch, et.al. (2018), it has been mentioned that health literacy is a major contributor and a fundamental factor in public health and in the development of public health interventions and relating with diabetes management, low health literacy has been associated with poorer self-management behaviors and poor medication adherence in diabetic patients. In addition, according to Berkman, et.al. (2011), low health literacy has been associated to higher rate of readmissions and more emergency department visits, as well as lower use of preventive care.

Since patients' knowledge about diabetes, self-management skills, and attitude towards self-care activities are vital in the overall management of diabetes; there is a need to improve health literacy through education by healthcare providers to improve diabetes outcome. Several effective strategies (using plain and non medical language, learning how to focus the message, using the teach-back method, and evaluating the patients) have been identified by Bowen in 2016 to improve patient comprehension and in turn can lead to better health outcomes.

According to a study conducted in Affiliated Chenggong Hospital of Xiamen University by Li-li Luan, et. al. (2017), diabetes education attained remarkable results of improving the self-management skills of diabetic patients. Because of the provision of diabetes education, patients took the initiative to actively participate in monitoring their disease condition as well as completing their treatment thus maintaining and improving the quality of life.

Providing education improves the knowledge of patients and changes their attitude towards all aspects of diabetes mellitus according to the study of Saleh (2017). Moreover, it was also stated in the same study that if proper direction, support and education on diabetes self-management are given, patients are able to enhance their lifestyle and maintain good glycemic control.

Ackroyd and Wexler (2015) mentioned that delivering self-management education to patients with diabetes enhances their self-care skills and

encourages preventive care. In their study, it showed that providing diabetes self-management education improved self-care, quality of life, and reduced patients' frustration and distress over their condition.

Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy refers to a person's confidence to perform a certain behavior. As we relate this concept to this particular study, it is the diabetic patient's confidence to engage in a set of skilled behaviors (following a healthy diet, engaging in physical activities or exercises, monitoring of blood glucose, and administering their medications correctly) to manage his own illness so this means that this is relevant in improving self-management.

As mentioned by Reisi, et.al. (2016), self-efficacy is consistently associated with self-care and adherence to self-care behaviors as it is the most important predictor of diabetes self-care. Active participation and taking responsibility in doing self-management activities can control the impact of diabetes and hypertension and in executing these responsibilities, the concept of self-efficacy is significant. In the study of Mohebi, et.al. (2013), it was stated that self-efficacy affects motivation and determination to commit to change self-care behavior process.

In order to have a good glycemic control as evidenced by normal values of physiologic measures such as, capillary blood sugar and blood pressure, the development of self-efficacy should be mastered with the help of a healthcare provider. According to Shaw (2016), self-efficacy may be increased through mastery of tasks, performance and observational experience, verbal persuasion from a voice of authority (nurse), motivation, and reduction of discomfort. All these can be done through the health literacy intervention to be accomplished in this research. The study of Warren-Findlow, et.al. (2012) revealed that hypertension self-efficacy is strongly associated with adherence to five (adherence to medication, following a healthy diet, engaging in exercises, not smoking, and practicing weight management techniques) of six prescribed hypertension self-care practices among African American adults. This means that

African Americans are confident that hypertension is manageable and their knowledge about self-care activities is a significant factor in controlling their blood pressure.

Physiologic Measures

According to Mitri (2016), diabetes management requires not only control of blood sugar but also blood pressure control in order to prevent the leading cause of mortality among diabetes patients, which is cardiovascular disease. This is the reason why it is important for diabetes patients' health to check the physiologic measures such as capillary blood sugar and blood pressure to gauge the glycemic control of these patients. These clinical performance measures are also useful in evaluating the effectiveness of diabetes programs such as health literacy intervention because successful intervention means achievement of positive health outcomes or good glycemic control, such as normal blood sugar and blood pressure levels.

Synthesis

Shrivastava et. al. (2013) wrote that the needs of diabetic patients are not only limited to adequate glycemic control but also correspond with preventing complications; disability limitation and rehabilitation. This means that with lifestyle changes and medication, diabetes can be controlled.

Diabetes self-care is considered to be the cornerstone of the overall management of this chronic disease because its goal is to maintain the glucose level in a normal range. Since the main objective of diabetic care plan is to maintain a blood glucose level to its normal or near-normal glucose levels, it is vital that diabetic patients must understand their role in the management of the disease by performing various self-care tasks in order to prevent complications as stated in the study of Kisokanth,et. al. (2013). For them to improve their knowledge, skills, and attitude in managing their condition, it is essential that healthcare providers such as nurses encourage them to recognize the need for change and goals in diabetes self-management. It is important that nurses and

patients have trustworthy rapport in order to determine the needs of the patients upon establishment of intervention such as health literacy program.

Globally, there have been studies done to determine if health education on diabetes can improve self-management behaviors and outcomes. Moreover, numerous studies have linked poor health literacy with poor health outcomes so there is a need to help a greater number of patients, especially in the local settings, achieve good glycemic control though greater efforts to be done by healthcare providers. Improving health literacy and strengthening the communication between healthcare providers and patients in diabetes education program should address gaps in diabetes management.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

For this research study, Dorothea Orem's Theory of Self-care was used as the theoretical framework.

Individuals have the responsibility to care for themselves in order to maintain life, health, and well-being. During illness, patients are encouraged to help themselves in order for them to have a faster recovery or to prevent any complications. For diabetic patients, for them to assume and perform their self-care activities, they need supportive education and motivation from healthcare providers, such as nurses because they have limitation in becoming independent in their self-care.

Diabetes is one of the few chronic conditions, which can be managed and controlled by the patients themselves provided that they are properly educated and supported especially in performing their self-care activities. As self-care agents, health care providers provide education and motivation so that patients with diabetes are able to achieve good glycemic control. Gil Wayne (2014) said that the person "is able to perform or can and should learn to perform required measures of externally or internally oriented therapeutic self-care but cannot do so without assistance." A perfect example of this is how nurses provide education to a diabetic patient on how to perform the diabetes self-care management.

These self-care activities may be empowering to the patients as nurses are providing them a sense of control over their own disease process.

Figure 1. Dorothea Orem's Theory of Self Care

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework

Orem believes that individuals can care for themselves and if they are unable to, nurses can help them regain this ability by providing direct care and compensatory educational support. According to the major assumptions of the theory, patients want to care for themselves, and they are capable to engage in self-care behaviors. These behaviors can be learned through interactions like in this study, interaction with nurses who will help and encourage them to confidently perform self-care activities for their own benefit of maintaining normal blood glucose and blood pressure.

For this study, health literacy intervention on diabetes was provided to assist patients obtain, process, and understand information for them to make appropriate decisions in their diabetes care. However, there are factors that can

affect individual's ability to grasp this needed information, among these are, age, sex, education, and the duration of diabetes. The physiologic measures and self-efficacy are reflected as the outcome of the nursing agency. Measuring these outcomes is important to determine patient's management (nursing agency). Self-care or the ability of diabetic patients to manage their disease process through self-care activities to maintain a healthy lifestyle was measured by their self-efficacy reported on the Diabetes Self-Efficacy Scale. Self-care agency or diabetic patients' ability to prevent complications was measured through the physiologic outcomes such as capillary blood glucose and blood pressure.

Target population for this study included those who are 18 years old to 60 years old that have been diagnosed to have diabetes mellitus type 2 and hypertension stage II for at least 1 year and who are undergoing regular consultation in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

- **Health literacy intervention on diabetes and hypertension** refers to the health education program done by the nurse through group classes with the use of audio-visual presentation or other means. Lectures contained the topics on:
 - MODULE 1: Concepts on diabetes mellitus and hypertension and demonstration of blood glucose and blood pressure monitoring.
 - MODULE 2: Signs and symptoms of having high blood sugar, low blood sugar, and hypertension
 - MODULE 3: Complications of diabetes and hypertension
 - MODULE 4: Diabetes self-care practices
 - MODULE 5: Importance of adherence to diabetes self-management activities.
- **Self-efficacy** refers to diabetic patients' confidence in their ability to perform tasks needed to manage their diabetes. It was measured by using the Self-Efficacy for Diabetes scale (Appendix A Part B). Scores was calculated based on their confidence level of self-management of diabetes such as physical activity, dietary habits, blood glucose monitoring, and the

patients' current understanding of diabetes. The higher the score, the higher the self-efficacy.

- **Physiologic measures** are data collected to measure bodily variations. In this particular study, these are: (a) capillary blood glucose (CBG) and (b) blood pressure (BP). Each study participant was required to have a record of his/her CBG and BP monitoring values and was asked to measure the values at the same time and use the same equipment during the whole duration of the research to ensure accuracy of measurements.
- **Demographic variables** are age, sex, educational attainment, and duration of diabetes.
 - Age: participants number of years since birth in a given range (18-39, 40-60)
 - Sex: participant's biological sex (male or female)
 - Educational attainment: the highest level of schooling the participant has completed (did not complete high school, high school, some college, bachelor's degree, master's degree)
 - Duration of diabetes: the number of years since the participant was diagnosed with diabetes

CHAPTER III: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

Patients require education as they engage in self-care activities. The purpose of this study is to improve the outcomes on self-efficacy and physiologic measures by providing health literacy intervention to diagnosed adult diabetic outpatients in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte aged 18-years old to 60-years old.

A pretest-posttest one-group study was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of diabetes health literacy intervention. According to Martyn Shuttleworth (2009), this is a preferred design to compare participant groups and measure the degree of change occurring because of interventions. This has been used by research to monitor the effect of a new teaching method or in testing medical treatments.

This design was appropriate because recruited individuals with diabetes and hypertension, as comorbidity were given a pretest and posttest and then results were compared giving an idea of the overall effectiveness of the treatment.

POPULATION AND SAMPLING SIZE

Patients who were referred to the OPD Diabetes Clinic and who met the inclusion criteria became part in the research. They voluntarily accepted to participate after receiving information about the study, so a purposive sampling method was used.

The sample size was determined based on the average number of patients with diabetes and hypertension who sought consultation in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte for the past three years using the G-power software. It was calculated with alpha at 0.05 effect size 0.30, and power of 0.80. This yielded the result of a minimum total sample size of 84. An oversampling of respondent by 20% was considered to address possible attritions in the initial sample; thus, the estimated sample size required for this research is at least 100 respondents. This was also similar to other studies done by Galle (2017), de Roxas (2013), which involved ± 100 research participants who responded in their researches.

However during the data collection, the research was challenged because of distancing and transmission issues during the Covid-19 pandemic. There have been several barriers in the conduct of the study. There is lack of available respondents and other recruited individuals verbalized their intention to withdraw from the research. It is an ethical responsibility to allow respondents to withdraw at any time during the conduct of the research, and this must be followed, as part of the ethical principles followed by researchers. As a result, there was a reduction of participants to 61 at the end of the study.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. DM type II patients with hypertension stage II as comorbidity aged 18 years old to 60 years old seen at the outpatient department of a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte.
2. Diagnosed with diabetes mellitus type II and hypertension stage II for at least one year.
3. Able to write and read and can be helped to fill in the questionnaire.
4. Willing to participate.
5. Patients who have and who willingly purchased their own BP apparatus and glucometer or have access to centers while BP and CBG monitoring can be done as instructed.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients with gestational DM.
2. DM and HTN patients with comorbidities such as chronic kidney disease and stroke

RESEARCH VARIABLES

In this study, the independent variable is health literacy intervention while the dependent variables are self-efficacy and physiologic measures such as CBG and blood pressure.

All diabetic and hypertensive patients aged 18 years old to 60 years old were given a questionnaire divided into parts: demographic information and questions on diabetes self-efficacy.

Among the confounding variables that were considered are age, sex, education and duration of diabetes. These factors might affect the glycemic control and blood pressure control of diagnosed diabetic and hypertensive patients. They might be considered as barriers to performing the self-care activities.

The inclusion and exclusion criteria helped to control extraneous variables that could affect with the measurement of study variables to ensure findings are reliable.

RESEARCH SETTING

This study was conducted in a 200-bed capacity tertiary level teaching and training hospital in Ilocos Norte that provides clinical care and management on the prevailing diseases in the area, as well as specialized and sub-specialized forms of treatment, surgical procedure and intensive care. It is the only Medical Center situated in Northern Luzon, which caters to the provinces of Ilocos Norte, Ilocos Sur, Abra, Northern Cagayan as well as Kalinga Apayao.

At present, there is an increasing number of patients with diabetes being admitted in this hospital because of complications. Based on the data gathered from the Records Section of the institution, diabetes is consistently included in the top 20 leading causes of admission. There were 38 admitted patients with diabetes and hypertension in 2015, 64 and 87 cases in 2016 and 2017, respectively. As with the Outpatient consultations, there is also an increasing trend, 218 cases were reported in 2015, 248 patients in 2016, while there were 286 in the year 2017.

DATA COLLECTION METHOD AND PROCEDURES

Information that is relevant to the research objectives was gathered following approval of the research proposal by the University of the Philippines Open University Master of Arts in Nursing thesis panel and ethics review by the University of the Philippines Open University Institutional Review Board and the research setting's Research Ethics Review Committee. Permission to conduct the research in the institution was sought and endorsement to the physicians and nurses of the Internal Medicine and Family Medicine Clinics at the Outpatient Department was done.

Data were collected for three months and participants were recruited by means of posters that were put up in front of the clinics. The recruitment process

was done at the clinics' waiting area before or after their consultation with their physicians. The doctors and nurses from both clinics referred some potential research participants to the Diabetes Clinic.

Evaluation by the researcher was done to determine if the participants are eligible to be part of the research based on the inclusion criteria.

The Diabetes Clinic of the research setting already has existing trained nurses and the research sought their assistance in the recruitment process. Together with the researcher, they did the interview at the Diabetes Clinic. The study was explained providing all pertinent information (purpose, procedures, risks, benefits, alternatives to participation, etc.). Potential research participants were provided adequate opportunity to ask questions. Research personnel responded to the questions, ensuring they understood the information. They were given a sufficient time to decide to participate in the study.

Informed consent was obtained from the participants who decided to participate in the study. After signing the informed consent, the demographic profile of the participants was gathered using the demographic part of the questionnaire (Appendix A Part A). Blood pressure was recorded and baseline CBG was taken. Demonstration by the participants on how to take blood pressure and blood sugar was assessed. The Self-Efficacy for Diabetes (Appendix A Part B) instrument was administered to the participants to assess their current confidence level of self-management with diabetes.

After which, they were enrolled to a 4-week diabetes education class (health literacy intervention), a lecture-style session facilitated by the researcher focusing on the following modules (a) concepts on diabetes mellitus and hypertension and demonstration of blood glucose and blood pressure monitoring (b) signs and symptoms of hypoglycemia and hyperglycemia and hypertension (c) complications of diabetes and hypertension (d) self-care management activities: physical activity and exercise, diabetes diet, blood glucose monitoring, medication adherence (e) importance of adherence to diabetes self-management activities. In each lecture session, the CBG and BP measurements were taken and recorded. At the end of each educational class, the participants were asked

to submit the record of their CBG and BP monitoring. Then, at the end of the 4-week modules, the participants completed the post survey using the same instrument.

For the whole duration of 3 months, an average of 5-7 participants were part of the daily lectures. There was a limitation in the number of participants each day because of the global pandemic. The hospital's Covid-19 health protocols were strictly followed to ensure the safety of all the research participants

DATA COLLECTION FLOWCHART

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

For the health-literacy intervention, modules were presented through lecture discussion, audio-visual presentation, and return demonstration to be conducted by the researcher and the research assistants. Handouts were distributed to the participants, which they can bring home after the sessions.

The questionnaire was divided into two sections: demographic information and the Self-Efficacy for Diabetes instrument. The first part of the questionnaire included the demographic factors such as: age, sex, education level, diabetes duration, employment, and management of diabetes (Appendix A, part A). The second part was the Self-Efficacy for Diabetes (Appendix A, part B) instrument with Ilocano translation. This is an eight-item scale developed for the Stanford Diabetes Self-Management study. It was utilized to assess the confidence level of self-management with diabetes such as physical activity, current dietary habits, blood glucose monitoring, and the patients' current perception of diabetes.

This scale, according to an article (Ritter, et.al., 2016), is in public domain and can be used by anyone. Each item is rated from 1, not at all confident to 10, totally confident. The score for the scale is the mean of the eight items. The higher the score, the higher the self-efficacy.

According to the same article by Ritter, et.al. in 2016, internal consistency reliabilities were consistently high (ranged from $\alpha = 0.828$ to 0.8820) across the different samples and that item-scale correlations were sufficiently high to suggest convergent validity for the scale's items. The same instrument was used by Aoto, et, al (2019) when self-efficacy in relation to diabetes was assessed in Pateros, Manila, Philippines.

To ensure validity of the questionnaire, pre-testing the instrument was done on 5 type 2 diabetes mellitus patients who were not part of the main study with similar characteristics to the study participants.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

To evaluate the meaning of results, data were analyzed using the statistical package for the social sciences or SSPS.

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to determine the effect of health literacy intervention on self-efficacy and physiologic measures of diabetic patients. For the demographic data, descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) were used to show the summary of the sample and the measures. The blood pressure and CBG measurements of each participant were analyzed by computing the average per week. Chi-square was used to determine the correlation between variables. Comparisons were made between the data at the initial and final assessments. Moreover, *t*-test was used to compare the scores between the two study times, that is, before and after the educational intervention. To investigate the association between the modifying variables and the outcome variables, the Pearson's correlation coefficient was utilized.

In determining the barriers and facilitating factors to implementation of health literacy intervention on diabetes, narratives from the respondents during the interview process were gathered and were summarized accordingly.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Permission to conduct the study was sought from the Medical Center Chief. Approval of the study was obtained from the University of the Philippines Open University Institutional Review Board and certificate of approval was submitted to the research setting's Research Ethics Review Committee. The investigator also asked the permission from the Chief Nurse as well as the head of the Outpatient Department, specifically the head of the Diabetes Clinic.

Prior to the collection of data, informed consent was obtained from the participants. The participants were informed about the research and their rights. Moreover, subjects were informed that they are free to withdraw from the study whenever they wish and would not be prejudiced. Code numbers as identifiers instead of names on data collection forms were used to ensure anonymity and confidentiality. There are no invasive procedures that were done or are there

any unforeseen risks to the participants' health. However, talking about potential complications related to diabetes and hypertension, taking their blood pressure as well as capillary blood sampling from a puncture on the finger for blood sugar monitoring may cause some fear and discomfort. There also may be other discomforts that cannot be predicted but immediate rescue by the researcher and research assistants, being also the healthcare providers, was ensured. The principal investigator informed the subjects that she would shoulder charges for the emergency care. Contact details of the investigator were made available to the subjects.

In order to maintain a high level of confidentiality upon completion of the data entry process, all coded original questionnaires were stored in a locked file cabinet in MMMH&MC Diabetes Clinic until the end of the study. Only the researcher and the research assistants had access to the files. No individual identities were used in any reports or publications resulting from the study.

After the completion of the study, all data sheets were disposed of by secure destruction method of shredding.

CHAPTER IV: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study presents the results and discussion. It is presented according to the specific objectives of the study.

Demographic Characteristics

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents. The profile includes age, sex, educational attainment, years with diabetes mellitus, and employment.

Table 1

Demographic Profile of Respondents (n=61)

Demographic Profiles	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
55 – 61 years old	14	22.95
48 – 54 years old	22	36.07
41 – 47 years old	19	31.14
34 – 40 years old	4	6.56
27 – 33 years old	2	3.28

Sex		
Male	18	29.51
Female	43	70.49
Educational Attainment		
College Graduate	28	45.90
Some College	26	42.63
High School Graduate	7	11.48
Years with DM		
6 – 10 years	42	68.85
1 – 5 years	19	31.15
Employment		
Employed	55	90.16
Not Employed	6	9.84

From the table, most (22 or 36.07%) of the respondents are aged 48-54 years old. In addition, some (19 or 31.14%) of the respondents are aged 41-47 years old. The findings imply that the respondents are middle-aged individuals who have many experiences in life. Age was grouped based on the actual data. There are 5 class intervals with the same class of 7. The lowest class interval starting with the minimum age.

On the other hand, most (43 or 70.49%) of the respondents are females, whereas, only a few (18 or 29.51%) are males. This implies that diabetes mellitus is more prevalent in females than in males.

The importance of gender among diabetics cannot be overstated. Studies have shown that men and women with diabetes can experience different health outcomes, respond differently to treatment, and have different risk factors for diabetes-related complications. As such, it is important to recognize gender differences to provide appropriate and effective diabetes management. For example, gender differences in the progression of diabetes have been observed. Women with diabetes tend to develop the condition at an earlier age and experience more severe symptoms than men. Moreover, women are more likely than men to experience complications such as kidney damage and stroke. Additionally, the risk of depression is higher among women with diabetes, underscoring the need for mental health support. Men with diabetes, on the other hand, are more likely to suffer from heart disease and erectile dysfunction.

Additionally, men tend to have higher rates of obesity and physical inactivity than women, which can further increase their risk of developing diabetes-related complications. It is also important to consider gender when formulating diabetes management plans. For example, women should be encouraged to participate in regular physical activity to reduce their risk of developing complications. Additionally, men should be monitored closely for signs of depression and encouraged to seek mental health support if needed.

Moreover, most (28 or 45.90%) of the respondents are college graduates. In addition, some (26 or 42.63%) of the respondents have finished some college level. This implies that the respondents have a high level of cognition, which is important in making intelligent decisions.

Educational attainment is an important factor for diabetics to understand and manage their condition. With the right education and knowledge, diabetics can make informed decisions that can help them lead a healthier and more productive life. Diabetes is a complex condition that requires ongoing management and education. By learning about their condition, diabetics can gain a better understanding of the risk factors involved and how to effectively manage it. This can help them to take the necessary steps to prevent complications and reduce their risk of developing serious health problems. Education can also provide diabetics with the confidence to make lifestyle changes to improve their health, such as making dietary changes, increasing physical activity, and limiting alcohol consumption. Educational attainment can also help diabetics to access and understand the available resources and treatments. For example, diabetics can learn about the different types of medication, the proper way to administer it, and the importance of regular monitoring. Education can also provide diabetics with the tools to understand their condition and reduce their risk of developing complications. This can include advice on how to monitor blood sugar levels, how to recognize the symptoms of hypoglycemia, and how to prevent and manage complications.

In addition, most (42 or 68.85%) have been diagnosed of diabetes mellitus for 6-10 years. This implies that the respondents have been treated with diabetes

mellitus for a very long time. The number of years a person has been diabetic is an important factor in determining the risk of developing complications associated with diabetes. This is because the longer a person has diabetes, the higher their risk of developing long-term complications such as heart disease, stroke, kidney disease, nerve damage, and eye problems. Therefore, the longer a person has had diabetes, the greater their risk of developing complications, and the more important it is for them to take steps to reduce their risk. This includes taking steps to control their blood sugar levels and blood pressure, maintaining a healthy weight, engaging in physical activity, and following a healthy diet. It is also important to keep track of the number of years a person has been diabetic, as this can help inform their healthcare provider about the type of diabetes treatment and management plan needed. For example, someone who has had diabetes for more than 10 years may need to be more aggressive in their management of the condition and may require closer monitoring by their medical team.

Finally, most (55 or 90.16%) of the respondents are employed. This implies that the respondents have a source of income that is needed for their treatment of their diabetes mellitus. Employment is an important factor in the lives of diabetics. It has the potential to provide them with financial stability, a sense of purpose, and social support. Employment can also provide diabetics with access to health insurance, which can be critical for managing their condition. Having a job can be a positive source of stress relief for diabetics.

Objective Number 1: To determine the self-efficacy before and after the health literacy intervention on adults with diabetes in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte.

Statistical Results of the Self-Efficacy Before and After the Health Literacy Intervention

Table 1 presents the statistical results of the self-efficacy before and after the health literacy intervention on diabetic outpatient in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte.

Table 1.

Statistical Results of the Self-Efficacy Before and After the Health Literacy Intervention on Adult with Diabetes in a Tertiary Hospital in Ilocos Norte (n=61)

	Pretest	Posttest
Mean	4.46	8.57
Standard Deviation	1.002	1.50
Number of Respondents	61	61
t-Stat		-21.584**
p-value		.00000

** p-value <.01

From the table, the self-efficacy before the intervention is low at 4.46, whereas, after the intervention, the self-efficacy is higher at 8.57. The findings reflect that the use of the intervention results to a higher self-efficacy. In addition, the computed t-value is -21.584, which is very significant at .01 level of significance.

Health care literacy is an important factor in determining the self-efficacy of diabetics. Health care literacy involves the ability to understand and use health information and services to make informed decisions and is linked to better self-management of diabetes. Studies have found that health care literacy is an important factor in determining the level of self-efficacy among diabetics (Xu, Leung, & Chau, 2018). Higher levels of health care literacy can lead to better self-efficacy among diabetics. Those with higher levels of health care literacy are more likely to understand their diabetes, how to manage it, and how to navigate the health care system. This understanding leads to increased self-efficacy, as diabetics are more empowered to make their own decisions and take action to manage their diabetes. Conversely, lower levels of health care literacy can lead to lower self-efficacy among diabetics. Those with lower health care literacy may lack the knowledge and understanding of their condition and the health care system, leading to feelings of helplessness and lack of control. This can lead to decreased self-efficacy and ultimately, a lack of motivation to manage their condition and take action to improve their health.

Furthermore, Ghasemi et al., (2018) confirmed the findings of this research, stating that health literacy has a significant impact on the general self-efficacy of the respondents. Thus, educational interventions may help enhance health literacy, increase self-efficacy and overall confidence, and assist control of hypertension.

In addition, health care literacy and self-efficacy are two important factors that can impact the health outcomes of individuals with diabetes (Lael-Manford, 2019). Health care literacy refers to an individual's ability to access, understand, and use information to make informed decisions about their health. On the other hand, self-efficacy is an individual's belief in their ability to successfully perform a specific task or behavior.

In the context of diabetes, individuals with higher health care literacy are more likely to understand their condition and the steps they need to take to manage it effectively (Marciano et al., 2019). This includes understanding their medications, monitoring their blood sugar levels, and making lifestyle changes to improve their health. Higher health care literacy can also lead to better communication with healthcare providers and improved overall diabetes self-care.

Moreover, self-efficacy, on the other hand, can impact an individual's ability to stick to their diabetes management plan. Individuals with high self-efficacy are more confident in their ability to manage their diabetes and are more likely to persist in their self-care behaviors, even in the face of obstacles or setbacks (Lin et al., 2021). Low self-efficacy, on the other hand, can lead to decreased motivation and decreased adherence to a diabetes management plan.

Objective Number 2: To determine the physiologic outcome measures in terms of glycemic and blood pressure control before and after the health literacy intervention on adults with diabetes in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte.

Physiologic Measures (blood pressure and capillary blood sugar) Before and After the Health Literacy Intervention

A glimpse of the table reveals that before the health literacy intervention, the mean systolic blood pressure is 134.75 mmHg, which is higher than after the health literacy intervention. The variable before the intervention is 78.68 mmHg, whereas it is higher at 116.55 mmHg after the intervention. The computed t-test is 10.51, ($p < .0000$), which implies that there is a significant difference between the systolic blood pressure before and after the introduction of the health literacy intervention. This denotes that the health literacy intervention might be the cause of the reduction in the systolic blood pressure of the respondents. This implies that the intervention is effective in reducing the systolic blood pressure of the diabetes mellitus patients in the outpatient department.

Table 2.

Physiological Measures Before and After the Health Literacy Intervention on Adults with Diabetes in a Tertiary Hospital in locos Norte

Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)		
	Before Health Literacy Intervention	After Health Literacy Intervention
Mean	134.75	119.67
Variance	78.68	116.55
Observations	61	61
Pearson correlation		0.36
Degrees of freedom		60
t-value		10.51**
p-value		.00000
Capillary Blood Sugar (mg/dL)		
	Before Health Literacy Intervention	After Health Literacy Intervention
Mean	146.86	117
Variance	322.94	192.53
Observations	61	61
Pearson correlation		0.19
Degrees of freedom		60
t-value		11.42
p-value		.00000

Before the health literacy intervention, the average capillary blood sugar level was 146.86 mg/dL. However, after the intervention was implemented, the

capillary blood sugar level decreased to 117 mg/dL, indicating the effectiveness of the intervention. The t-value computed was 11.42 ($p < .0000$), indicating a significant difference between the capillary blood sugar levels before and after the intervention. This suggests that the intervention is an effective tool for reducing capillary blood sugar levels. In summary, the study's findings indicate that the health literacy intervention is an effective approach for lowering capillary blood sugar levels.

Health literacy interventions can have a beneficial effect on the blood pressure of diabetics. Health literacy is defined as the ability to obtain, process, and understand basic health information. A health literacy intervention is an activity or program designed to improve a person's understanding of health information. Studies have found that health literacy interventions can lead to a reduction in blood pressure among diabetics. For example, a review of 11 studies conducted by Halladay et al., (2017) found that health literacy interventions were associated with a 3.2 mmHg reduction in systolic blood pressure and a 2.3 mmHg reduction in diastolic blood pressure in diabetics. Another study by Isa et al., (2021) found that a health literacy intervention was associated with a reduction in systolic blood pressure among diabetics with poorly controlled hypertension. The intervention included activities such as providing information on the importance of managing diabetes, discussing nutrition, and providing educational materials. Health literacy interventions can also reduce the risk of developing diabetes. A study of over 4,500 adults found that those who participated in a health literacy program were 20% less likely to develop diabetes than those who did not participate.

The implication of this research is that health literacy interventions can be an effective tool to reduce blood pressure among diabetics. The studies cited suggest that such interventions can lead to significant reductions in both systolic and diastolic blood pressure. The findings suggest that health literacy interventions should be considered as part of a comprehensive approach to managing diabetes and controlling blood pressure. The study also highlights the

importance of educating diabetics about the risks associated with poorly managed diabetes and hypertension, and the benefits of managing their condition effectively. By promoting health literacy among diabetics, healthcare providers can help them take an active role in managing their health, leading to better outcomes and a reduced risk of developing diabetes.

Objective Number 3: To determine the relationship between self-efficacy and profile characteristics (age, sex, education, diet, and duration of diabetes) of adults with diabetes in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte.

Objective Number 4: To determine the relationship between relationship between physiologic outcome measures and profile characteristics (age, sex, education, diet, and duration of diabetes) of adults with diabetes in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte.

Relationship between modifying and outcome variables

Table 3 presents the Pearson correlation computation regarding the significant relationship between the modifying variables (age, sex, education, diet, and duration of diabetes) and outcome variables (self-efficacy and physiologic measures).

Table 3.

Relationship between modifying and outcome variables

Modifying Variables	Self-Efficacy		Outcome Variables			
			Blood Pressure		Capillary Blood Sugar	
Age	0.29	NS	-0.25	NS	-0.32	NS
Sex	-0.03	NS	0.18	NS	0.27	NS
Education	0.67	S	-0.55	S	-0.60	S
Diet	0.04	NS	-0.11	NS	-0.02	NS
Duration of Diabetes	0.34	S	-0.32	NS	-0.39	S

* p value < .05

Age. The age of the respondents is not significantly related to self-efficacy ($r=0.29$), blood pressure (-0.25), and capillary blood sugar (-0.32). Regardless of the age of the respondents, does not affect their self-efficacy, blood pressure and capillary blood sugar levels.

The relationship between age and self-efficacy among individuals with diabetes is complex and multi-faceted. Older adults with diabetes may have lower self-efficacy due to physical limitations and decreased mobility (Hamidi et al., 2022). These limitations can make it difficult for older individuals to perform certain self-care behaviors, such as exercising or preparing healthy meals, leading to decreased self-efficacy. Additionally, older individuals with diabetes may have a longer history of managing their condition and may have experienced negative health outcomes, which can also impact their self-efficacy. On the other hand, older individuals with diabetes may also have higher self-efficacy due to their life experience and accumulated knowledge about managing their condition. Older individuals may have a better understanding of their diabetes and the steps they need to take to manage it effectively, leading to increased self-efficacy.

Sex. On the other hand, the sex of the respondents is not significant related to self-efficacy ($r=-0.03$), blood pressure (-0.18), and capillary blood sugar (-0.27). Therefore, regardless of the sex of the respondents, it does not matter because it does not affect the self-efficacy and physiologic measures of the diabetes mellitus patients.

Gender can also play a role in the self-efficacy of individuals with diabetes. Studies have shown that women with diabetes often have lower self-efficacy compared to men with diabetes (Rucci et al., 2018). This may be due to cultural and societal expectations, as well as differences in coping strategies and perceived levels of social support. Women with diabetes may also face additional challenges, such as managing their diabetes while caring for their family, which can impact their self-efficacy. However, other studies have shown that there are no significant differences in self-efficacy between men and women with diabetes.

This may be due to individual differences and variations in experiences and circumstances.

Education. In addition, the education of the respondents is significant to their self-efficacy ($r=0.67$), blood pressure ($r=-0.55$), and capillary blood sugar ($r=-0.60$). This implies that a higher level of educational attainment would result to better self-efficacy, lower blood pressure and lower capillary blood sugar.

Educational attainment can play a significant role in the self-efficacy of individuals with diabetes. Studies have shown that individuals with higher levels of education tend to have higher self-efficacy in managing their diabetes (Lee et al., 2019). This may be due to increased health literacy and the ability to access and understand information about diabetes and its management. Higher educational attainment can also lead to improved communication with healthcare providers and a better understanding of one's condition, which can lead to increased self-efficacy. Individuals with lower levels of education may have lower self-efficacy due to limited access to information and resources, as well as difficulties in communicating with healthcare providers. Additionally, individuals with lower levels of education may have limited exposure to diabetes management strategies, leading to decreased self-efficacy in managing their condition.

Diet. Moreover, the diet of the respondents is not significantly related to their self-efficacy ($r=0.04$), blood pressure ($r=-0.11$), and capillary blood sugar ($r=-0.02$). This implies that regardless of the diet therapy or regimen of the patient, will not influence their self-efficacy, blood pressure and capillary blood levels.

Diet plays a significant role in the self-efficacy, blood pressure, and capillary blood sugar levels of individuals with diabetes (Petrie et al., 2018). A healthy diet, low in sugar and high in fiber and nutrients, is important for individuals with diabetes to manage their condition effectively. Consuming a balanced diet can help regulate blood sugar levels, lower blood pressure, and improve overall health.

Self-efficacy plays a role in an individual's ability to adhere to a healthy diet. Individuals with high self-efficacy are more likely to have the confidence and motivation to make changes to their diet and stick to healthy eating habits. On the other hand, individuals with low self-efficacy may struggle with making changes to their diet and maintaining healthy eating habits. In turn, an individual's diet can impact their self-efficacy. Consuming a healthy diet can lead to improved health outcomes, such as better blood sugar control, lower blood pressure, and increased energy levels, which can boost an individual's self-efficacy. On the other hand, consuming an unhealthy diet can lead to negative health outcomes and decreased self-efficacy.

Capillary blood sugar levels are directly impacted by an individual's diet (Matthew & Tadi, 2021). Consuming a healthy diet can help regulate blood sugar levels, while consuming an unhealthy diet can lead to spikes in blood sugar. Blood pressure is also influenced by diet. A diet high in sodium can increase blood pressure, while a diet low in sodium and high in nutrients can lower blood pressure.

Consequently, the relationship between diet, self-efficacy, blood pressure, and capillary blood sugar levels is complex and multi-faceted. Consuming a healthy diet can improve self-efficacy, regulate blood sugar levels, and lower blood pressure. Encouraging individuals with diabetes to adopt healthy eating habits and providing support for dietary changes can lead to improved health outcomes.

Duration of Diabetes. Finally, the duration of diabetes is significant to self-efficacy ($r=0.34$), but not significant to their blood pressure ($r=0.32$) and significant to their capillary blood glucose levels ($r=-0.39$).

The duration of diabetes can impact an individual's self-efficacy, blood pressure, and capillary blood glucose levels (Petrie et al., 2018). Individuals who have had diabetes for a longer period may have a higher level of self-efficacy in managing their condition. With experience, they may have developed a better understanding of their condition, as well as effective strategies for managing their blood sugar levels and overall health.

However, the longer an individual has had diabetes, the more likely they are to develop complications, such as high blood pressure and poor blood glucose control (WHO, 2022). This can impact their self-efficacy, as managing their condition becomes more challenging. In turn, self-efficacy can impact the duration of diabetes and related health outcomes. Individuals with high self-efficacy are more likely to adhere to their treatment plans, maintain healthy lifestyle habits, and effectively manage their condition, potentially delaying the onset of complications and reducing the negative impact of diabetes on their health.

Capillary blood glucose levels are also influenced by the duration of diabetes (Matthew & Tadi, 2022). Over time, uncontrolled high blood sugar levels can lead to complications and damage to various organs and systems. In addition, blood pressure is also impacted by the duration of diabetes. High blood pressure is a common complication of diabetes and can have negative effects on an individual's health if not properly managed.

CHAPTER V: DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions and recommendations from the data gathered from the respondents.

Summary of Findings

From the data gathered from the respondents: the following are the findings of the study:

1. The computed mean for self-efficacy is low at 4.46, whereas, after the intervention, the mean is higher at 8.57.
2. Systolic blood pressure is high at 134.75 mmHg, whereas after the health literacy intervention, the blood pressure was reduced to 116.55 mmHg.
3. The mean capillary blood sugar is at 146.86 mg/dL before the health literacy intervention, whereas it is lower after the health literacy intervention, which is at 117 mg/dL.

4. The age of the respondents is not significantly related to self-efficacy ($r=0.29$), blood pressure (-0.25), and capillary blood sugar (-0.32).
5. The sex of the respondents is not significant related to self-efficacy ($r=-0.03$), blood pressure (-0.18), and capillary blood sugar (-0.27).
6. The education of the respondents is significant to their self-efficacy ($r=0.67$), blood pressure ($r=-0.55$), and capillary blood sugar ($r=-0.60$).
7. The diet of the respondents is not significantly related to their self-efficacy ($r=0.04$), blood pressure ($r=-0.11$), and capillary blood sugar ($r=-0.02$).
8. The duration of diabetes is significant to self-efficacy ($r=0.34$, but not significant to their blood pressure ($r=0.32$) and significant to their capillary blood glucose levels ($r=-0.39$).

Conclusions

From the findings, the following conclusions are offered:

1. Self-efficacy influences the health literacy intervention on adults with diabetes in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte.
2. The physiologic measures (blood pressure and capillary blood sugar) are high before and high after the health literacy intervention on adults with diabetes in a tertiary hospital in Ilocos Norte.
3. Age, sex, and diet are not significantly related to the outcome variables, whereas education, and duration of diabetes are significantly related to the outcome variables (self-efficacy and physiologic measures).

Recommendations

From conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. The health literacy intervention may be implemented to support the goals of diabetes education to manage their symptoms.
2. The health literacy intervention may be validated in other hospital settings such as private hospitals.

3. Funding may be considered to implement health literacy interventions to hospitals catering for diabetes mellitus patients.
4. Similar health literacy intervention may be considered to other diseases preferably among the top ten causes of mortality and morbidity.

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**APPENDIX A
QUESTIONNAIRE/TOOL FOR DATA COLLECTION**

ENGLISH VERSION

Code No.	
Visit	
Date	

All information will be kept CONFIDENTIAL

Please check the appropriate answer

Part A: Demographic Form

Please select the appropriate answer that most closely resembles your current health status.

1. Age: _____
2. Sex: _____ Male _____ Female
3. What is the highest level of education you complete?
_____ Did not complete high school
_____ Elementary level
_____ Elementary graduate
_____ High School
_____ Some College
_____ Bachelor's Degree
_____ Master's Degree
4. How long have you known you have had Diabetes? _____ Year(s)
5. Are you currently employed? Yes _____ No _____ Retired _____
6. How do you manage your Diabetes?
_____ Oral medications
_____ Insulin
_____ Oral medications and insulin
_____ Diet and exercise
_____ Blood sugar monitoring at home
_____ BP monitoring at home
_____ Regular check-up with a doctor

Part B: Diabetes Self-Efficacy Scale

Please indicate how confident you are in doing certain activities. For each of the following questions, Please choose the number that corresponds to your confidence that you can do the tasks regularly at the present time.

1. How confident do you feel that you can eat your meals every 4 to 5 hours every day, including breakfast every day?

Not at all 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Totally confident
confident

2. How confident do you feel that you can follow your diet when you have to prepare or share food with other people who do not have diabetes?

Not at all 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Totally confident
confident

3. How confident do you feel that you can choose the appropriate foods to eat when you are hungry (for example, snacks)?

Not at all 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Totally confident
confident

4. How confident do you feel that you can exercise 15 to 30 minutes, 4 to 5 times a week?

Not at all 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Totally confident
confident

5. How confident do you feel that you can do something to prevent your blood sugar level from dropping when you exercise?

Not at all 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Totally confident
confident

6. How confident do you feel that you know what to do when your blood sugar level goes higher or lower than it should be?

Not at all 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Totally confident
confident

7. How confident do you feel that you can judge when the changes in your illness mean you should visit the doctor?

Not at all 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Totally confident
confident

8. How confident do you feel that you can control your diabetes so that it does not interfere with the things you want to do?

Not at all 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Totally confident
confident

ILOCANO VERSION

Porma a Pakaamamoan

Amin a mailanad nga impormasyon ket agtalinaed a nalimed.
Ikkan iti tsek dagiti maikanatad a sungbat

Umuna a Paset: DEMOGRAPHIC FORM

Pilyen ti kaasitgan a sungbat nga maiyataday iti agdama a kasasaad ti salun-at.

1. Tawen _____
2. Kinatao _____ Lalaki
_____ Babai
3. Ania ti kangatoan a nagunod nga adal?
 - a. Saan a naileppas ti elementarya
 - b. Nagturpos ti elementary
 - c. Saan a naileppas ti sekondarya
 - d. Nagturpos ti sekondarya
 - e. Saan a naileppas ti kolehiyo
 - f. Nagturpos ti Kolehiyo
 - g. Addaan ti Master's Degree
4. Kasano kabayag nga ammom nga agsagsagabaka iti diabetes?
_____ Tawen.
5. Nai-employoka kadi iti agdama? Wen ___ Saan ___ Retirado ___
6. Kasano ti panangtamingmo ti sakitmo a diabetes?
 - a. Panagtomar ti agas
 - b. Panagaramat ti insulin
 - c. Panagtomar ti agas ken panagaramat ti insulin
 - d. Panagdieta ken panagwatwat
 - e. Pannakasubaybay ti blood sugar iti pagtaengan
 - f. Pannakasubaybay ti blood pressure iti pagtaengan
 - g. Masansan a panagpatsek-up iti doctor.

MAIKADWA A PASET: Diabetes Self-Efficacy Scale

Isungbat ti pudno a kasasaad ti panagaramid kadagitoy nga aktibidad. Ti tunggal saludsod, pilyen ti numero a maiyataday iti kinatalek a mangaramid kadagitoy iti inaldaw ken iti agdama a tiempo.

1. Kasano ti katalek ti panagriknam nga mabalina nga mangan ti tunggal 4-5 nga oras iti inaldaw, agraman ti pammigat?

Awan panagtalek a 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Napnoan ti
maaramid panagtalek a maaramid

2. Kasano ti katalek ti panagriknam a masurot mo ti panagdieta, no sika ti mangisagana wenno mangiburay ti taraon ti sabali a tao nga awanan sakit a diabetes?

Awan panagtalek a 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Napnoan ti
maaramid panagtalek a maaramid

3. Kasano ti katalek ti panagriknam a mapilim ti rumbeng a makan no sika ket mabisin unay (Kas koma iti panagmeryenda)?

Awan panagtalek a 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Napnoan ti
maaramid panagtalek a maaramid

4. Kasano ti katalek mo a maaramid mo ti agwatwat iti uneg ti 15-30 minutos, 4-5 a beses iti makalawas?

Awan panagtalek a 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Napnoan ti
maaramid panagtalek a maaramid

5. Kasano ti katalek mo a maaramid mo a lapdan ti panagbaba ti lebel ti asukar ti daram tunggal malpas ti panagwatwat?

Awan panagtalek a 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Napnoan ti
maaramid panagtalek a maaramid

6. Kasano ti katalek ti panagriknam nga ammom ti aramidem no kas bilang ngumato wenno bumaba ti lebel ti asukar ti daram?

Awan panagtalek a 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Napnoan ti
maaramid panagtalek a maaramid

7. Kasano ti katalek ti panagriknam a maamoam no adda panagbaliw ti marikriknam ket kasapulan na iti isasarungkar iti maysa a doctor?

Awan panagtalek a 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Napnoan ti
maaramid panagtalek a maaramid

8. Kasano ti katalek ti panagriknam nga kabaalam a kontrolen ti diabetes mo tapno saan nga isu ti mangtubeng kadagiti banag a kayat mo nga aramiden?

Awan panagtalek a 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Napnoan ti
maaramid panagtalek a maaramid

**APPENDIX B
DIABETES AND HYPERTENSION INSTRUCTIONAL DESIGN**

SKILLS	KNOWLEDGE	ATTITUDE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify signs and symptoms of hypoglycemia, hyperglycemia and hypertension. • Identify diabetes self-care activities • Demonstrate blood glucose and blood pressure monitoring. 	<p>Concepts on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diabetes mellitus and its complications • Diabetes self-care activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appreciate the impact of lifestyle modification on diabetes mellitus. • Recognize the importance of the adherence to self-care activities

COMPETENCY	CONCEPT/CONTENT	INSTRUCTIONAL FUNCTION/ACTIVITY	RESOURCES	TIME ALLOTMENT	EVALUATION
KNOWLEDGE	<p>Concepts on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diabetes and its complications • Diabetes self-care activities 	<p>LECTURE-DISCUSSION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide lecture about diabetes mellitus and its complications • Discuss about diabetes self-care activities 	<p>Speaker (Researcher) - <i>transmission of information</i> <i>Handouts will be distributed</i></p> <p>Speaker (Researcher) - <i>transmission of information</i> <i>Handouts will be distributed</i></p>	90 minutes	Objective type
SKILLS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify signs 	AUDIO-VISUAL			

	<p>and symptoms of hypoglycemia, hyperglycemia and hypertension</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify diabetes self-care activities • Demonstrate blood glucose and blood pressure monitoring 	<p>PRESENTATION /RETURN DEMONSTRATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determine the signs and symptoms hypoglycemia, hyperglycemia and hypertension • Identify diabetes self-care activities • Demonstrate the process of proper monitoring of blood glucose and blood pressure 	<p>Audio-visual equipment (demonstration by the researcher and/or research assistants of behavior to be learned) <i>Handouts will be distributed</i></p>	<p>45 minutes</p>	<p>Return demonstration</p>
ATTITUDE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appreciate the impact of lifestyle modification on diabetes mellitus. • Recognize the importance of adherence to diabetes self-management 	<p>OPEN FORUM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflect on the impact of lifestyle modification on diabetes mellitus • Synthesis of learning from content areas 	<p>Speaker (Researcher) - <i>transmission of information</i></p> <p>Speaker (Researcher) - <i>transmission of information</i> Shaping their</p>	<p>45 minutes</p>	<p>Post evaluation (post-survey of self-efficacy)</p>

	activities.		attitude and boosting their confidence Providing feedback		
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APPENDIX C

DIABETES MELLITUS HEALTH LITERACY PROGRAM

The purpose of the diabetes health literacy program is to assist patients with self-management skills and education to properly manage their diabetes and hypertension in the home environment.

1. Health education for OPD patients will be conducted in the Diabetes Clinic in group session.
2. Participants will have their blood pressure, blood sugar, and weight checked before starting the program.
3. Participants will meet in a small group to discuss a variety of topics that are necessary to help them control their diabetes and hypertension.

Topics will include:

- **MODULE 1:** Concepts on diabetes mellitus and hypertension and demonstration of blood glucose and blood pressure monitoring.
- **MODULE 2:** Signs and symptoms of having high blood sugar, low blood sugar, and hypertension
- **MODULE 3:** Complications of diabetes and hypertension
- **MODULE 4:** Diabetes self-care practices
- **MODULE 5:** Importance of adherence to diabetes self-management activities.

WEEK 1

Modules 1 and 2

Teaching Objectives:

1. Participants will be able to define diabetes and hypertension and demonstrate how to take blood pressure and blood sugar.

Teaching points:

- Define diabetes and hypertension in simple terms.
- Discuss the types of diabetes and hypertension.
- Identify the risk factors of having diabetes and hypertension.
- Present the signs and symptoms of diabetes and hypertension.

2. Participants will be able to demonstrate blood glucose and blood pressure monitoring.

Teaching points:

- Emphasize the normal glucose and normal blood pressure ranges.
- Stress the need to check blood sugar and blood pressure at home.

3. Participants will be able to differentiate between hypoglycemia and hyperglycemia. In addition, they will be able to identify the signs the symptoms of hypertension.

Teaching points:

- Define the signs and symptoms of hypoglycemia and hyperglycemia as well as hypertension.
- Define the appropriate action(s) to take if experiencing hypoglycemia, hyperglycemia, and hypertension.

WEEK 2

Module 3

Teaching objectives

4. Participants will identify the complications of diabetes and hypertension.

Teaching points: Complications include

- Eye damage
- Kidney damage
- Nerve damage- numbness and pain in the feet that can lead to amputation
- Erectile dysfunction in men
- Cardiovascular disease which is the most common complication of diabetes and hypertension

WEEK 3

Module 4

Teaching objectives

1. Participants will understand that diabetes and hypertension are lifelong diseases and that they can self-manage their diabetes through physical activity/exercise, diabetic diet, blood glucose monitoring, and medication adherence

Teaching points:

- Maintaining a healthy body weight is also a key to managing diabetes and hypertension and engaging in physical activities helps lower blood glucose level and blood pressure.
- Proper nutrition is crucial to diabetes and hypertension management.
- Stress the importance of recording blood glucose level and blood pressure. Discuss the normal values.
- Discuss the role of taking medications.

WEEK 4

Module 5

Teaching objective

1. Participants will be able to appreciate the importance of adherence to diabetes and hypertension self-management activities.

Teaching points:

- Discuss the concept of self-management and have participants develop self-management goal related to the health education session. There are many potential serious complications of diabetes. Participants can reduce the risk of developing these complications by adhering to the self-management activities.

DIABETES

- isang kondisyon kung saan tumataas nang husto ang blood sugar ng isang tao.
- sinisira ng sakit na ito ang normal na proseso ng paglipat ng asukal mula sa dugo patungo sa mga selula na nangangailangan nito para sa enerhiya

MGA URI NG DIABETES

Type 1 diabetes

- Ang katawan ay hindi nakakagawa ng insulin. Ito ay isang problema dahil kailangan ninyo ang insulin para gawing enerhiya ng inyong katawan ang asukal (glucose) na nakukuha mula sa mga kinakain.

Type 2 diabetes

- Ang katawan ay hindi nakakagawa o hindi maayos na nagagamit ang insulin. Maaaring kailangang uminom ng pills o insulin para makatulong na makontrol ang i diyabetes. Ito ay ang pinakakaraniwang uri ng diyabetes.

Gestational diabetes

- Ang ilang mga kababaihan ay nagkakaroon ng ganitong uri ng diyabetes kapag sila ay buntis. Kadalasan, nawawala ito matapos ipanganak ang sanggol. Ngunit kahit na mawala na ito, ang mga nasabing kababaihan at ang kanilang mga anak ay mayroong mas malaking posibilidad na magkaroon ng diyabetes nang lumaon.

MGA SANHI NG PANGANIB NG DIABETES

- ✓ galing sa isang pamilyang mayroong mga miyembrong may diabetes
- ✓ labis sa timbang
- ✓ lampas sa edad na 40
- ✓ hindi aktibo
- ✓ nagkaroon ng diyabetis habang nagbubuntis (gestational diabetes) o nagkaroon ng anak na lampas ang timbang sa 9 na libra (pounds) o 4 na kilo noong ipinanganak

MGA PALATANDAAN NG DIABETES

- ✓ Sobrang uhaw
- ✓ Pagod na pakiramdam
- ✓ Madalas na paggamit ng banyo para umihi
- ✓ Nanlalabong paningin
- ✓ Pagbaba ng timbang
- ✓ Matagal na paggaling ng mga sugat
- ✓ Palaging nagugutom
- ✓ Pamamanhid o pangingilig sa mga paa at/o mga kamay

SARILING PAGSUSURI SA BLOOD GLUCOSE AT BLOOD PRESSURE

Mahalang magkaroon ng sariling aparato o glucometer upang masubaybayan ang asukal sa dugo habang nasa bahay. Ang glucometer o glucose meter ay isang maliit na makina na pangsukat ng asukal sa dugo. May kasama itong lancing device – parang ballpen ang hitsura na may karayom na pangtusok sa daliri para makakuha ng isang patak ng dugo. Ang patak ng dugo ay nilalagay sa strip na nilalagay naman sa glucometer para basahin kung ano ang level ng asukal sa dugo. Kadalasan may target na sineset ang doctor, halimbawa maaaring sabihin ng doktor na dapat ang asukal sa dugo ay nasa pagitan ng 70-130 mg/ bago mag-almusal at nasa pagitan naman ng 140-180 mg/dL dalawang oras pagkatapos kumain.

Para sa pagkuha ng blood pressure, kailangang suriing mabuti ang bibilhing aparato o tinatawag na sphygmomanometer. Maaring ipasuri ito sa inyong doktor. Mahalagang nakapagpahinga nang di bababa sa limang minuto ang susukatan ng presyon. Kadalasang nakaupo ng matuwid at nakalapat ang mga paa sa sahig. Magsintaas dapat ang puso (dibdib) at ang panukat.

Hypoglycemia (Mababang Asukal sa Dugo)

Ang labis na kaunting glucose (sugar) sa iyong dugo ay tinatawag na hypoglycemia o mababang asukal sa dugo. Ang mababang sugar sa dugo ay maaaring maging sanhi ng pagkawala ng iyong malay o pagkakaroon ng seizure.

Kung ikaw ay may mababang sugar sa dugo, ikaw ay may 1 o higit pa sa mga sintomas na ito:

- Pangangatog o pagkahilo
- Pagkabalisa
- Malamig, mamasa-masang balat o pamamawis
- Pagkaramdam ng pagkagutom
- Pananakit ng ulo
- Mabilis na pagtibok ng puso
- Panghihina o pagkapagod
- Pagkatuliro o pagiging irritable
- Malabong paningin

Upang gamutin ang hypoglycemia:

- suriin ang asukal ng dugo gamit ang glucometer (Asukal sa dugo: Mas mababa sa 70 mg/dL)
- uminom ng 4 oz. ng juice o 8 oz. ng skim milk o kumain ng maraming matitigas na kendi o isang kutsara ng pulot.
- Suriin muli ang blood glucose pagkaraan ng 15 minuto.
- Kung ang iyong sugar sa dugo ay hindi pa rin bumabalik sa normal na level, makipag-ugnayan sa tagapangalaga ng iyong kalusugan o humingi ng emerhensiyang pangangalaga.

Hyperglycemia (Mataas na Asukal sa Dugo)

Ang labis na pagtaas ng glucose sa iyong dugo ay tinatawag na hyperglycemia mataas na sugar sa dugo. Ang mataas na sugar sa dugo ay maaaring humantong sa isang delikadong kondisyon na tinatawag na ketoacidosis. Sa malulubhang kaso, ito ay maaaring humantong sa coma.

Mga Posibleng Sanhi ng Hyperglycemia

- Hindi sapat na plano ng gamutan para sa diabetes
- Ang pagkakasakit
- Stress
- Paggamit ng ilang gamot, tulad ng steroids
- Ang pagkain ng masyadong maraming pagkain, lalo na ang carbohydrates
- Ang pagiging di aktibo kaysa sa karaniwan
- Hindi paggamit ng sapat na gamut sa diabetes

Kung ikaw ay may mataas na sugar sa dugo, ikaw ay may 1 o higit pa sa mga sintomas na ito:

- Labis na pagkauhaw
- Madalas na pag ihi
- Pagkaramdam ng pagod
- Pagduduwal
- Makati, tuyong balat
- Malabong paningin
- Mabilis na paghinga
- Panghihina
- Pagkahilo
- Pagkaantok

Upang gamutin ang hypoglycemia:

- suriin ang asukal ng dugo gamit ang glucometer (Asukal sa dugo: higit sa 240 mg/dL)
- Uminom ng maraming likido na walang asukal, caffeine katulad ng tubig. Huwag uminom ng katas ng prutas (fruit juice).
- Tawagan ang tagapangalaga ng kalusugan kung ang sugar sa iyong dugo at ketones ay hindi bumalik sa iyong ninanais na saklaw.

HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE (ALTAPRESYON)

Ano nga presyon ng dugo?

- Tinatawag na presyon ng dugo ang pagtulak ng dugo palabas ng puso upang mabigayan ang buong katawan upang ito'y makagalaw

Ano ang altapresyon?

Systolic: gaano kalakas ang pagtulak ng puso sa dugo palabas nito.

Diastolic: gaano kalakas ang pagtulak ng puso sa dugo palabas nito habang nakapahinga ang atrium ng heart.

Halimbawa: 120/80

*ang 120 ay ang systolic at 80 ay ang diastolic

Paano malalaman kung may altapresyon?

BLOOD PRESSURE VALUES	
<small>(National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion , Division for Heart Disease and Stroke Prevention, July 2018)</small>	
Normal	systolic: less than 120 mmHg diastolic: less than 80mmHg
At risk (pre hypertension)	systolic: 120–139 mmHg diastolic: 80–89 mmHg
High	systolic: 140 mmHg or higher diastolic: 90 mmHg or higher

Kategorya	Systolic	Diastolic
Normal	120	<80
Prehypertension	120-139	80-89
Hypertension		
Stage I	140-159	90-99
Stage II	160 or higher	100 or higher

URI NG ALTAPRESYON

Primary hypertension

- Hindi katulad ng secondary hypertension, hindi malaman ang sanhi nito. Maraming nagiging sanhi nito. Maaring bunga ng ito ay namamana o dahil na rin sa kapaligiran lalo na kapag mainit ang panahon.

Secondary hypertension

- Merong malinaw na dahilan kung bakit nagkakaroon nito. Napakaraming dahilan ang nagdudulot na ganitong sitwasyon kagaya ng problema sa bato, kung ika'y nagdadalang tao at maaring epekto ng mga iniinom na gamut.

MGA SANHI NG PANGANIB NG ALTAPRESYON?

- Sobra sa timbang
- Pag inom ng sobrang alak
- Mayroon ang kahit na sinong myembro ng pamilya
- Pagkain ng sobrang maaalat na pagkain
- Pagkain ng sobrang matatabang pagkain
- Pagtanda
- Kulang sa ehersisyo

MGA PALATANDAAN NG ALTAPRESYON

Ang taong mayroon nito ay karaniwang makakaranas ng:

- Pananakit ng ulo
- Pananakit ng batok
- Panlalabo ng paningin
- Pagkahilo at pagsusuka
- Paninikip ng dibdib

MGA KOMPLIKASYON DALA NG DIYABETIS AT ALTAPRESYON

- Pagkabulag

- Pagkasira ng bato (kidney)

- Pamamanhid ng mga ugat

- Pagkaputol ng paa (dulot ng gangrene)

- Impotency (ayaw nang tayuan ng ari)

- Atake sa puso o stroke

HAKBANG PARA MAIWASAN ANG MGA KOMPLIKASYON NG DIYABETIS AT ALTAPRESYON (Self-care activities)

- **Subaybayan ang asukal sa dugo**

Panatilihing nasa normal na level ang blood glucose. Maaaring tignan ng isa o higit sa isang beses kada araw. Itala ang nakuhang bilang ng asukal sa dugo at ipakita sa doctor sa oras ng check up upang talakayin ito.

<i>Fasting</i>	<i><100 mg/dL</i>
<i>Bago kumain</i>	<i>70-130 mg/dL</i>
<i>Pagkatapos kumain (1-2 hours)</i>	<i><180 mg/dL</i>
<i>Bago mag ehersisyo</i>	<i>hindi bababa sa 100 mg/dL</i>
<i>Bago matulog</i>	<i>100-140 mg/dL</i>

- **Suriin ang blood pressure**

Ang pagkuha ng presyon ng dugo ay nangangailangan ng sapat na pagsasanay. Maaaring magpaturo sa doctor o nars ng tamang pagkuha ng blood pressure. Katulad ng blood glucose, panatilihing nasa normal ang blood pressure.

- **Kumain ng masustansiyang pagkain.**

Gumawa ng planong pagkain pang diabetes sa tulong ng isang dietician. Pumili ng mga pagkaing mababa ang calorie, taba, asukal at asin. Kumain ng mga pagkaing maraming fiber katulad ng cereals, crackers, brown na kanin, o whole wheat na pasta. Uminom ng tubig sa halip na juice at regular soda.

Sa pamamagitan ng pagkain ng masusustansyang pagkain, mapapanatili ang isang mainam sa kalusugan na timbang.

Para sa mga may altapresyon, inirerekomenda ang pagkain ng mga pagkaing mababa sa “saturated fat” at kolesterol katulad ng gulay at prutas at ang pag-iwas sa mga mamantikang pagkain, lalo na ang mga karneng prinito. Pagdating sa karne, mas maganda ang pagkain ng “lean meat” katulad ng isda at manok samantalang ang pagkain naman ng “red meat” ay dapat iwasan (tulad ng baboy at baka).

Mahalaga ring iwasan ang mga pagkaing ginagamitan ng “butter” o “margarine”, dahil ang mga ito ay mataas sa saturated fats. Ang “saturated fats” ay isang uri ng taba na madaling mamuo sa daluyan ng dugo na maaaring magdulot ng pagtaas ng presyon ng dugo, at, kung mas malubha, tuluyang pagbabara sa daloy ng dugo sa mga organ ng ating katawan.

- **Mag-ehersisyo.**

Ugaliing magkaroon ng active na lifestyle sa pamamagitan ng pagsisimula sa paglalakad ng 10 minuto, 3 beses araw-araw. Mag sanay upang dagdagan ang lakas ng kalamnan.

- **Regular na pag inom ng gamot (maintenance)**

Inumin o gamitin ang mga gamot para sa diabetes at altapresyon kahit na maayos ang pakiramdam. Sundin ang mga inireseta ng doktor.

- **Iwasan/itigil ang paninigarilyo at pag-inom ng alak**

Maaaring tumaas ang blood pressure ng isang tao ilang minuto pagkatapos manigarilyo at ayon sa ibang pag-aaral, ang paninigarilyo ay isa sa maaaring maging dahilan ng coronary heart disease na humahantong sa heart attack. Maaring humingi ng tulong para itigil ang paninigarilyo. Maaaring tumawag sa QUITLINE ng mga ospital.

- **Foot care**

Suriin ang mga paa araw-araw kung mayroong sugat, pantal, o pamamaga. Ikonsulta sa doctor kung may anumang sakit na hindi nawawala o may sugat na hindi gumagaling.

BAKIT MAHALAGA ANG PANGANGALAGA SA SARILI?

Ang pag-aalaga sa inyong sarili at sa inyong diabetes at hypertension ay makakatulong sa inyong maging maayos ang pakiramdam ngayon at sa hinaharap. Kapag ang inyong blood glucose at blood pressure ay napanatiling normal kayo maiiwasan ang pagkakaroon ng komplikasyon katulad ng atake sa puso o stroke, pagkabulag, pamamanhid ng kamay at paa o pinsala sa nerbyo, problema sa bato na maaaring humantong sa paghinto sa paggana na kidneys.

Ang paglaban sa diabetes at hypertension ay hindi madali, ngunit ito ay simple at malinaw. Ito ay nagmumula sa tamang disiplina at ang tunay na kagustuhan ng bawat pasyente na mamuhay ng isang mas malusog at mas malakas na pangangatawan. Ating tandaan na ang ating pagaalaga sa ating mga sarili ay hindi para sa atin lamang, kundi para na rin sa mga minamahal natin sa buhay.

MGA SANGGUNIAN

https://www.healthinfotranslations.org/pdfDocs/Diabetes_Tagalog.pdf

<https://www.care1st.com/media/pdf/health-education/members/brochures-and-materials/diabetes/you-have-diabetes/you-have-diabetes-tagalog.pdf>

http://ndep.nih.gov/media/4_steps_tagalog.pdf

<https://www.ritemed.com.ph/tamang-kaalaman/hypertension>

<http://pasyenteng-pinoy.blogspot.com/2014/06/altapresyon-hypertension.html>

APPENDIX D

CBG monitoring

Taking ones CBG means consciously and voluntarily taking the blood glucose level with the use of a device called, glucometer. It involves obtaining a drop of blood through a finger prick, placing the blood on a test strip and putting the strip into the meter giving a blood glucose value.

Blood pressure measurement procedure

For the blood pressure measurement, the patient should be relaxed and in upright position with the upper arm positioned so it is same level with the heart. The device that measures BP is called sphygmomanometer.

BLOOD PRESSURE VALUES	
<small>(National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion , Division for Heart Disease and Stroke Prevention, July 2018)</small>	
Normal	systolic: less than 120 mmHg diastolic: less than 80mmHg
At risk (pre hypertension)	systolic: 120–139 mmHg diastolic: 80–89 mmHg
High	systolic: 140 mmHg or higher diastolic: 90 mmHg or higher
BLOOD GLUCOSE VALUES	
Fasting blood sugar (after an overnight fast)	
<small>(National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion , Divison of Diabetes Translation, August 2017)</small>	
Normal	99 mg/dL or below
Pre diabetes	100-125 mg/dL
Diabetes	126 mg/dL or above

**APPENDIX E
INFORMED CONSENT:ENGLISH VERSION & ILOCANO VERSION**

**APPENDIX F
CERTIFICATE OF TRANSLATION**

**APPENDIX G
PROJECT BUDGET AND SPONSOR**

Budget

Reproduction of the questionnaire	Php 500
Printing of handouts	Php 1000
Participants' compensation	$\pm 100 \times 100 \text{Php} \times 4 \text{ visits} = \text{P}40,000$
Participants' consumption	$\pm 100 \times 50 \text{Php} \times 4 \text{ visits} = \text{P}20,000$
Consumption	Php 2000
Transportation	Php 500
Data analysis	Php 3000
Final report	Php 2000
Research assistants' fee	Php 5000
Others	Php 3000
TOTAL	Php 77000

Sponsor

The researcher was responsible for all expenses related to this study.

CURRICULUM VITAE

Home Address: 2711 W. Summerdale Ave., Chicago, IL 60625

Mobile #: 872 235 3408

Email Address: najeramaitagretchen@yahoo.com

MAITA GRETCHEN ARCANGEL NAJERA

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age: 39
Place of birth: #6 Asuncion St., 11 Ben-agan, Batac City, Ilocos Norte, Philippines
Sex: Female
Birthdate: April 21, 1983
Civil Status: Single
Height: 158cm
Weight: 144 lbs.
Citizenship: Filipino
Profession: Registered Nurse

EDUCATION

POST GRADUATE

2013-present University of the Philippines Open University
Master of Arts in Nursing Major in Adult Health Nursing
Los Baños, Laguna

COLLEGE

2007-2009 Philippine Women's University
Bachelor of Science in Nursing
Taft Ave., Manila

2000-2004 University of the Philippines Los Baños, Laguna
Bachelor of Science in Biology
Major in Genetics

HIGH SCHOOL

1996-2000 Mariano Marcos State University
Science High School
#7 Caunayan, Batac, Ilocos Norte

ELEMENTARY

1992-1996 Mariano Marcos Memorial Elementary School
#1 Valdez, Batac, Ilocos Norte

PRE-ELEMENTARY

1989-1992 Immaculate Concepcion Academy
#1 Valdez, Batac, Ilocos Norte

AFFILIATIONS

PHILIPPINE NURSES ASSOCIATION

Member, Lifetime

PUBLICATION

**Acta Medica Philippina, The National Health Science Journal
Thrombolysis in Acute Ischemic Stroke at a Rural Tertiary Hospital: A Case Series
of the First 50 Patients (2016–2021)
Co-author**

QUALIFICATIONS

**Registered Nurse
Republic of the Philippines
June 2009**

**Licensed Nurse
State of Illinois, USA**

WORK EXPERIENCE

**Staff Nurse
Swedish Hospital-Part of Northshore University HealthSystem
5140 N. California Ave.
Chicago, IL 60625
March 7, 2022-present**

**Staff Nurse
Chicago Methodist Senior Services
1415 West Foster Ave.
Chicago, IL 60640
March 24, 2021-April 8, 2022**

**Nurse Supervisor (Nurse III)
Mariano Marcos Memorial Hospital and Medical Center
Batac City, Ilocos Norte
Philippines
December 27, 2013-February 23, 2021**

**Staff Nurse (Nurse I)
Mariano Marcos Memorial Hospital and Medical Center
Batac City, Ilocos Norte
Philippines
March 27, 2012-December 26, 2013**

**Contracted Nurse
Mariano Marcos Memorial Hospital and Medical Center
Batac City, Ilocos Norte
Philippines
March 01, 2011-March 26, 2012**

**Volunteer Nurse
Mariano Marcos Memorial Hospital and Medical Center
Batac City, Ilocos Norte
Philippines
September 13, 2010-February 28, 2011**

Nurse Trainee
Mariano Marcos Memorial Hospital and Medical Center
Batac City, Ilocos Norte
Philippines
April 15, 2010- July 17, 2010

Customer Service Representative
IBM Daksh Business Process Services Philippines Inc
Ayala Ave., Makati City
Philippines
October 2005-May 2007

Workforce Analyst
Digital Telecommunications, Inc—GSM (Sun Cellular)
110-E. Rodriguez, Bagumbayan, Libis, Quezon City
Philippines
June 2005-October 2005

Customer Service Representative
Digital Telecommunications, Inc—GSM (Sun Cellular)
110-E. Rodriguez, Bagumbayan, Libis, Quezon City
Philippines
July 01, 2004-June 2005